

Editors

- **Barna Iantovics**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania
 - **Dumitru Rădoiu**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania
 - **Marius Mărușteri**, University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Targu Mures, Romania
 - **Matthias Dehmer**, Institute for Bioinformatics and Translational Research, The Health and Life Sciences University (UMIT), Hall in Tyrol, Austria
-

Preface

This Special Issue entitled *Complexity in Sciences and Artificial Intelligence* contains selected papers presented at the *International Symposium on Understanding Intelligent and Complex Systems - UICS 2009*, held on 22-23 October 2009 at Petru Maior University of Targu Mures from Romania. The primary aim of this symposium was bringing together researchers who work in the areas such as Complex Systems, Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Systems, Natural Computing, Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Sciences for presenting their recent results. The secondary purpose was to make some preparative steps in the realization of researches in the frame of certain research projects focused on themes like: Applications in Medical Sciences, Complex Systems and Artificial Intelligence. One of the approved research projects is entitled “*Electronic Health Records for the Next Generation Medical Decision Support in Romanian and Bulgarian National Healthcare Systems*” abbreviated as *NextGenElectroMedSupport*. *NextGenElectroMedSupport*, a Bilateral Cooperation Research Project between Romania and Bulgaria having as directors of project from Bulgaria Prof. dr. Roumen Kountchev from Technical University of Sofia and from Romania Senior Lecturer dr. Barna Iantovics from Petru Maior University of Targu Mures. The preferred topics of the symposium included developments in theory and practice by analyzing intelligent and complex systems. Particular research interests were the analysis of aspects related to intelligent and complex systems such as various problems dealing with complexity, intelligence, applications in medical sciences and further related aspects.

The papers included in this Special Issue shed light upon some introductory and advanced problems in the following areas: complex systems, natural computing, social insect algorithms, mathematical methods, pattern recognition, graph theory, semantic graphs, intelligent systems, intelligent prediction, modelling group decision processes, pharmaceutical sciences, emergence of life, human consciousness and society, data mining, learning algorithms, categorical ontology of complex systems and highly difficult problems solving.

Editors of the Special Issue & Editor in Chief of the B.R.A.I.N. Journal

This Special Issue contains selected papers presented at the International Symposium on Understanding Intelligent and Complex Systems - UICS 2009, held on 22-23 October 2009 at Petru Maior University of Targu Mures, Romania.

<http://uics.upm.ro>

Scientific Organizer

- **Barna Iantovics**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania

Honorary Chairs

- **Florin Gheorghe Filip**, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania
- **Liviu Marian**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania
- **Calin Enachescu**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania

Symposium General Chair

- **Barna Iantovics**, Petru Maior University, Romania

Program Chair

- **Dumitru Radoiu**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania

Publication Chair

- **Barna Iantovics**, Petru Maior University, Targu Mures, Romania

Secretary

- **Camelia Ilies**, Petru Maior University, Romania
- **Marcel Bogdan**, Petru Maior University, Romania

Scientific Committee

- **Florin Gheorghe Filip**, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania
- **Dan Dumitrescu**, Babes-Bolyai, University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Akira Namatame**, National Defense Academy, Japan
- **Viorel Negru**, West University, Timisoara, Romania
- **Matthias Dehmer**, Institute for Bioinformatics and Translational Research, The Health and Life Sciences University (UMIT), Austria
- **Xiufen Yu**, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China
- **Florentin Smarandache**, University of New Mexico, New Mexico, USA
- **Ventzeslav Valev**, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria
- **Madan M. Gupta**, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, Canada
- **Ioan Dzitac**, Aurel Vlaicu University, Arad, Romania
- **Rodica-Mariana Ion**, Valahia University, Targoviste, Romania
- **Kazumi Nakamatsu**, University of Hyogo, Japan
- **Horacio Wio**, Universidad de Cantabria, Santander, Spain
- **Daniel Breaz**, "1 Decembrie 1918" University, Alba Iulia, Romania

- **Manfred Gruber**, University of Applied Sciences, Munich, Germany
- **Ronald R. Yager**, Machine Intelligence Institute, New Rochelle, USA
- **Barna Iantovics**, Petru Maior University, Tg. Mures, Romania
- **Cyrille Bertelle**, Le Havre University, France
- **James Glazebrook**, Eastern Illinois University, Illinois, USA
- **Taleb-Bendiab Azzelarabe**, Liverpool John Moores University, Liverpool, UK
- **Constantin-Bala Zamfirescu**, Lucian Blaga University, Sibiu, Romania
- **Calin Enachescu**, Petru Maior University, Tg. Mures, Romania
- **Hai-Bin Duan**, Beihang University, Beijing, China
- **Aziz Alaoui**, Le Havre University, France
- **Marcin Paprzycki**, Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland
- **Militon Frentiu**, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Valentina Emilia Balas**, Aurel Vlaicu University, Romania
- **Angel Garrido**, Facultad de Ciencias, UNED, Madrid, Spain
- **Gabriela Serban**, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Rajiv Dharaskar**, GH Rasoni College of Engineering, Nagpur, India
- **Sabin Buraga**, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, Iasi, Romania
- **Horia Florin Pop**, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Sidorenco Veaceslav**, Technical University, Chisinau, Moldova
- **Mihai Talmaciu**, University of Bacau, Romania
- **Bazil Parv**, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Kamisetty R. Rao**, University of Texas at Arlington, USA
- **Dumitru Radoiu**, Petru Maior University, Tg. Mures, Romania
- **Alaa Sheta**, Al-Balqa Applied University, Jordan
- **Marius Balas**, Aurel Vlaicu University, Romania
- **Jair M. Abe**, Paulista University, Brazil
- **Elena Nechita**, University of Bacau, Romania
- **Giulia Rotundo**, University of Tuscia, Roma, Italy
- **I.C. Baianu**, University of Illinois at Urbana, USA
- **Costin Badica**, University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania
- **Tamas Szantai**, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary
- **Marusteri Marius**, University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Tg. Mures, Romania
- **Florin Nichita**, "Simion Stoilow" Institute of the Romanian Academy, Romania
- **Sugata Sanyal**, Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai, India
- **Laszlo Kovacs**, University of Miskolc, Hungary
- **Camelia Chira**, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

External Reviewers

- **Piroska Haller**, Petru Maior University, Tg. Mures, Romania
- **Andrzej Gecow**, Warsaw University of Technology, Poland
- **Bogdan Crainicu**, Petru Maior University, Tg. Mures, Romania
- **Edith Kovacs**, AVF College of Management Budapest, Hungary
- **Bela Genge**, Petru Maior University, Tg. Mures, Romania

Editorial Board of the journal

Editor in chief

- **Bogdan Patrut**, "Vasile Alecsandri" University of Bacau, Romania

Editorial Board

- **Ioan Andone**, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Romania
- **Ovidiu Andronesi**, Athinoula A. Martinos Center for Biomedical Imaging, Massachusetts General Hospital and Harvard Medical School, Charlestown, Boston, United States of America & "Babes-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Constanta Bodea**, Academy of Economic Studies, Bucharest, Romania
- **Gianluca Ceriani**, DACOM Srl, Milan, Italy
- **Doina Cmeciu**, "Vasile Alecsandri" University of Bacau and Europe Direct centre in Bacau, Romania
- **Svetlana Cojocar**, Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, Chisinau, Moldavia
- **Louise Connell**, University of Manchester, United Kingdom
- **Domenico Consoli**, University of Urbino, Italy
- **Doru Costache**, St Andrew's Greek Orthodox Theological College, Sydney College of Divinity, Sydney, Australia
- **Mariana Costache**, "M. Costache" Psychology Office, Bacau, Romania
- **Dan Cristea**, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Romania
- **Gabriela Czibula**, "Babes-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Mattias Dehmer**, Institute for Bioinformatics and Translational Research, The Health and Life Sciences University (UMIT), Austria
- **Claudia Diamantini**, Polytechnic University of Marche, Ancona, Italy
- **Gheorghe Dumitriu**, "Vasile Alecsandri" University of Bacau, Romania
- **Ioan Dzitac**, "Aurel Vlaicu" University of Arad, Romania
- **Angel Garrido**, Faculty of Sciences, National University of Distance Education, Madrid, Spain
- **Pat Hayes**, director of AAAI, Institute for Human and Machine Cognition, affiliated with several Florida universities, United States of America
- **Annette Hohenberger**, Cognitive Science Department, Informatics Institut, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Turkey
- **Barna Iantovics**, "Petru Maior" University of Targu Mures, Romania
- **Daniela Jeder**, "Stefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, Romania
- **Parvaneh Khosravizadeh**, Sharif University of Technology, Islamic Republic of Iran
- **Heather K J Van Der Lely**, Department of Psychology, Harvard University United States of America and Centre for Developmental Language Disorders and Cognitive Neuroscience, United Kingdom
- **Manuel López-Ibáñez**, IRIDIA, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium
- **Lorenzo Magnani**, University of Pavia, Italy and Sun-Yat Sen University, Canton, China
- **Georgios K. Matis**, Democritus University of Thrace, Medical School, Neurosurgical Department, University Hospital of Alexandroupolis, Greece
- **Ioan Maxim**, "Stefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, Romania
- **Ana-Maria Minut**, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Romania
- **Grigor Moldovan**, "Babes-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Elena Nechita**, "Vasile Alecsandri" University of Bacau, Romania
- **Bogdan Patrut**, "Vasile Alecsandri" University of Bacau, Romania
- **Iulia Karin Patrut**, University of Trier, Germany
- **Valeriy Perminov**, Belovo Branch of Kemerovo State University, Russian Federation
- **Camelia Mihaela Pinte**, "Babes-Bolyai" University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
- **Zvezdan Pirtosek**, University Medical Centre, Ljubljana, Slovenia
- **Bogdan O. Popescu**, Romanian Society of Neurology, Bucharest, Romania
- **Merritt Ruhlen**, Department of Anthropological Sciences, Stanford University, United States of America

- **Iolanda Tobolcea**, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Romania
- **Piedad Yuste Lecifena**, Faculty of Philosophy, Department of Philosophy, National University of Distance Education, Madrid, Spain
- **Zdzislaw Wasik**, Philological School of Higher Education in Wroklaw, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, International Communicology Institute, Poland
- **Nora Wiedenmann**, Munich, Germany

B.R.A.I.N. Journal Indexing Services

Our journal is currently indexed in the following academic indexing services and international databases:

- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- EBSCO (EBSCO Open Access Computer Science, EBSCO Open Access Journals, EBSCO Open Access Medical and Health Collection)
- IndexCopernicus
- The Linguist List
- Google Academic
- Ulrichs
- getCITED
- Genamics JournalSeek
- Zeitschriftendatenbank (ZDB)
- J-Gate
- SHERPA/RoMEO
- Dayang Journal System
- Public Knowledge Project
- BIUM (Bibliothèque interuniversitaire de médecine et d'odontologie)
- NewJour
- ArticleReach Direct
- Link+
- CSB (Collection of Computer Science Bibliographies)
- CiteSeerX

Some universities and organizations list our journal in their online libraries:

- Geneva Foundation for Medical Education and Research
- BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine)
- River Campus Libraries (Univ. of Rochester)
- Tulips (University of Tsukuba Library))
- Showa University Library
- Keio University (Shinanomachi Media Center)
- University of Pennsylvania
- University of Modena and Reggio Emilia
- Tel Aviv University, Gitter-Smolarz Library of Life Sciences and Medicine
- National Autonomous University of Mexico, Genomic Sciences Center, Institute of Biotechnology
- Saint Petersburg State University
- University of Puerto Rico
- Vrije Universiteit Brussel

- Queensland University of Technology
- The University of Queensland
- University of Florida
- John Brown University
- Université Paris-Descartes
- University of Regensburg
- Michigan State University
- University of Colorado Boulder
- University of Glasgow
- Washington University in Saint Louis
- Wayne State University
- California State University, Long Beach
- Brown University, Providence, Rhode Island
- The University of Hong Kong
- University of Nevada, Reno
- Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München
- Dowling College, New York State
- Colgate University, New York State
- Lewis and Clark College
- York University
- Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México
- University of Gothenburg (Göteborgs universitet)
- University of Saskatchewan
- Université du Québec à Montréal
- Feng Chia University, Taiwan